

Estimation and comparison of Serum C-reactive Protein Levels in Oral Sub mucous fibrosis and Oral Cancer: A Cross Sectional Study

Abstract

Background:

Oral cancer, predominantly oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC), is a major public health concern in India. Oral potentially malignant disorders (OPMDs), such as oral submucous fibrosis (OSMF), are recognized precursors of OSCC. Chronic inflammation plays a critical role in oral carcinogenesis, and C-reactive protein (CRP), an acute-phase inflammatory marker, has emerged as a potential prognostic biomarker. However, limited evidence exists regarding its role in OPMDs.

Aim:

To evaluate and compare serum CRP levels in patients with oral submucous fibrosis, oral squamous cell carcinoma, and healthy controls.

Materials and Methods:

This cross-sectional study included 300 participants divided into three groups: 100 patients with OSMF, 100 patients with OSCC, and 100 age- and sex-matched healthy controls. All cases were clinically and histopathologically confirmed. Serum CRP levels were measured using a quantitative turbidimetric method. Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS version 22.0. Group comparisons were conducted using one-way ANOVA and the Kruskal–Wallis test, followed by post hoc pairwise comparisons using the Dwass–Steel–Critchlow–Fligner method. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.001$.

Results:

Mean serum CRP levels increased progressively from healthy controls (3.32 ± 1.33 mg/L) to OSMF patients (14.37 ± 7.82 mg/L) and were highest in OSCC patients (49.33 ± 24.81 mg/L). The differences among the three groups were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), with post hoc analysis confirming significant intergroup variations.

Conclusion:

Serum CRP levels show a significant association with disease severity, supporting its role as a marker of inflammation in oral carcinogenesis. CRP may serve as a simple and cost-effective prognostic biomarker for oral potentially malignant disorders and oral cancer.

Keywords:

C-reactive protein; Oral squamous cell carcinoma; Oral submucous fibrosis; Oral potentially malignant disorders; Inflammation; Biomarker

Authors:

First and corresponding author

Dr. Hetul Patel

Associate Professor

Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology, Faculty of Dental Sciences, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, India

Second

Dr. Hiren Patel

Dean, Professor & Head

Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Faculty of Dental Sciences, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, India

Third

Dr. Bhupesh Patel

Professor & Head

Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Pathology, Faculty of Dental Sciences, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, India

Fourth

Dr. Priti Shah

Professor & Head

Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology, Faculty of Dental Sciences, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, India

Fifth

Dr. Chirag Patel

Associate Professor

Department of Pedodontics and Preventive Dentistry, Faculty of Dental Sciences, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, India

Sixth

Dr. Meghna Pujara

Associate Professor

Department of Periodontology, Faculty of Dental Sciences, Dharmsinh Desai University, Nadiad, India

Source of support: Nil

Conflict of interest: None

Introduction

Cancer remains one of the most devastating diseases worldwide. Among cancers of the head and neck region, oral cancer is the most common, with an annual global incidence of approximately 300,000 cases.¹

In India, oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) ranks first in incidence among men and third among women.² The country consistently reports one of the highest global burdens of oral cancer and oral potentially malignant disorders (OPMDs), with more than 100,000 new oral cancer cases registered annually.³ It is linked to the use of alcohol, betel nuts, tobacco, and other tobacco products. It results in high rates of morbidity and mortality, as well as financial, social, and familial difficulties. OSCC is associated with one of the lowest 5-year survival rates among all cancers, largely due to late-stage diagnosis. Nevertheless, when detected at an early stage, the prognosis and survival outcomes improve significantly compared with many other cancer types.²

Oral submucous fibrosis (OSMF) is a potentially malignant condition characterized by chronic inflammation in the juxta-epithelial region, leading to epithelial atrophy and progressive fibrosis. It is strongly associated with habitual areca nut consumption.⁴ The alkaloids and flavonoids present in areca nut act as chronic irritants, inducing gradual fibrotic changes within the oral mucosa. In addition, repeated microtrauma from the chewing habit contributes to juxta-epithelial inflammatory cell infiltration, further accelerating disease progression.⁵

This condition can lead to progressive restriction in mouth opening, subsequently impairing food intake, oral hygiene practices, and speech. Early identification of OSMF and timely intervention aimed at addressing its etiological factors are crucial for halting disease progression and reducing the risk of malignant transformation.⁶

Potentially malignant disorders (PMDs) serve as important precursors to oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC), characterized by cellular and architectural alterations that increase the likelihood of carcinogenesis. While advanced oral cancer is typically straightforward to diagnose, its early manifestations are often subtle and may easily go unnoticed.⁷

Early diagnosis and appropriate management of oral potentially malignant disorders (OPMDs) have been shown to prevent malignant transformation in up to 88% of cases, contributing to disease downstaging and reduced mortality.⁸⁻¹⁰ Consequently, there is a pressing need for cost-effective and reliable biomarkers capable of detecting these lesions at an early stage. A substantial body of evidence has demonstrated a strong association between cancer and inflammation. Chronic inflammation is recognized as a key contributor to carcinogenesis, influencing cancer initiation, promotion, and progression, and thereby increasing overall cancer incidence.¹¹

C-reactive protein (CRP), first identified by Tillet and Francis in 1930, is an acute-phase protein synthesized primarily by hepatocytes in response to mediators released by adipocytes.¹² Its production is regulated by pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-1 (IL-1), interleukin-6 (IL-6), and tumour necrosis factor (TNF), all of which have been implicated in various malignancies. Elevated IL-6 levels, in particular, have

been shown to correlate with increased CRP concentrations in patients with head and neck cancers.¹³

The prognostic significance of CRP has been well documented across a wide range of systemic malignancies, including lung, breast, colorectal, esophageal, hepatic, pancreatic, renal and urinary tract cancers, as well as hematological cancers and sarcomas.^{14,15} Its role in oral cancer has also been investigated, with several studies reporting promising diagnostic and prognostic outcomes.¹⁶⁻¹⁸ However, only a limited number of studies^{19,20} have explored the utility of CRP in oral potentially malignant disorders (OPMDs). This gap in the literature underscores the need for further research in this area.

Therefore, the present study was designed to evaluate CRP levels in patients with oral submucous fibrosis and oral cancer, and to compare these findings with those of healthy individuals.

Materials and Method

A permission to conduct the present study was obtained from Institutional Ethics Committee. (IEC). this study was conducted at Department of Oral Medicine & Radiology, Faculty of Dental Sciences, DDU, Nadiad. The study population consisted of clinically and histopathologically diagnosed and untreated hundred Patients having Oral Submucous Fibrosis - Group I , hundred Patients having Oral squamous cell carcinoma - Group II and hundred age and sex matched healthy controls for comparison of results - Group III. The selection of samples was by means of random sampling. Participants of any age group and irrespective of gender included in the study. Participants included in control group was free from any type of systemic disease, both in past & present.

Information about this study was given to each participant in the vernacular language or in the language of understanding through Information Sheet. The Participation in this study was Voluntary. The Informed Consent form was signed by each participant who wish to participate in this study, before the oral examination and blood collection. Each participant was interviewed. Structured questions related to vital statistics, education, oral health related complaints, medical history, detail history of habits esp. related to Tobacco and Areca nut consumption etc. was asked to each participant and the outcome for the same was recorded in the specially designed pre-tested "Proforma". Thorough oral examination was performed by two subject specialists. The oral examination was performed with the help of diagnostic instruments with necessary aseptic precautions and with both- direct and indirect light. A standard oro-facial examination method recommended by WHO was used to examine each participant: (a) the extra-oral, head and neck areas; and (b) peri-oral and intra-oral soft tissues. The following oral mucosal areas were examined sequentially in detail - lips, buccal and vestibular mucosa, hard and soft palate, tongue, floor of mouth, oro- pharynx etc. After clinical diagnosis of lesion free mouth or mouth having lesion – irrespective of severity and type of OSMF or oral cancer, patients were selected.

After histopathological confirmation the patients was recalled. Venous blood was collected using a sterile disposable syringe and the blood sample was allowed to clot, serum was extracted and stored at 2-8° c till subjected for C-Reactive Protein test. CRP in

serum is stable for 7 days at 2-8° c. The equipment used to estimate serum C-Reactive Protein level in present study is spectrophotometer measured by turbidimetry. This is the mode of quantitative test which gives the accurate reading. Serum C-Reactive Protein causes agglutination of the latex particles coated with anti human C-Reactive Protein. The agglutination of the latex particles is proportional to the CRP concentration and is measured by turbidimetry. The normal reference range considered as 0-6 mg/l. The findings were entered in the proforma.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data was subjected to statistical analysis by using a statistical software, IBM SPSS v. 22.0. The tests applied were descriptive statistics, one way anova and posthoc tukey test to compare the three groups. non parametric analysis is done using Kruskal Wallis test and Post hoc pairwise comparisons using the Dwass–Steel–Critchlow–Fligner method. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.001$.

Results

Table 1 shows the One way anova and posthoc tukey test to compare the three groups.

	OSMF (N=100) Mean \pm SD	OSCC (N=100) Mean \pm SD	Control (N=100) Mean \pm SD	F / Welch Statistics (* represents welch test)	P value	OSMF vs OSCC Difference (p value)	OSMF vs Control Difference (p value)	OSCC vs Control Difference (p value)
age(yrs.)	39.26 \pm 12.51	52.68 \pm 11.1	32.3 \pm 9.48	97.736 *	<0.001	13.42(<0.001)	6.96(<0.001)	20.38(<0.001)
serum CRP levels - mg/l	14.37 \pm 7.82	49.33 \pm 24.81	3.32 \pm 1.33	265.156 *	<0.001	34.96(<0.001)	11.06(<0.001)	46.01(<0.001)

Comparison of the parameter age(yrs.) between the three groups showed significant difference between the three groups (test value of 97.736 and p value of <0.001). The highest mean values were seen in OSCC (52.68 \pm 11.1) followed by OSMF (39.26 \pm 12.51) and Control (32.3 \pm 9.48). Subgroup analysis using posthoc Tukey HSD test shows that the largest difference between the groups was noted between OSCC vs Control (20.38) which was significant, followed by OSMF vs OSCC (13.42, significant) and OSMF vs Control (6.96, significant).

Comparison of the parameter serum CRP levels -mg/l between the three groups showed significant difference between the three groups (test value of 265.156 and p value of <0.001). The highest mean values were seen in OSCC (49.33 \pm 24.81) followed by

OSMF (14.37 ± 7.82) and Control (3.32 ± 1.33). Subgroup analysis using posthoc Tukey HSD test shows that the largest difference between the groups was noted between OSCC vs Control (46.014) which was significant, followed by OSMF vs OSCC (34.957, significant) and OSMF vs Control (11.057, significant).

The Shapiro–Wilk test for normality revealed that age showed a p-value of 0.070, indicating a normal distribution, whereas serum CRP levels showed a significant deviation from normality ($p < 0.001$). Since serum CRP levels were not normally distributed, non-parametric analysis using the Kruskal–Wallis test was employed for both age and serum CRP levels to ensure uniform comparison across all variables.

Tabel 2 shows The Shapiro–Wilk test for normality

Normality Test (Shapiro-Wilk)		
	W	p
age(yrs.)	0.991	0.070
serum CRP levels -mg/l	0.848	<.001

Note. A low p-value suggests a violation of the assumption of normality

Tabel 3 shows Kruskal Wallis test (Non-parametric)

Descriptives										
								Percentiles		
	Group	N	Missin g	Mea n	SD	Minimu m	Maximu m	25th	50th	75th
age(yr s.)	OSMF	10 0	0	39.2 6	12.5 1	19	67	28.7 5	37.0 0	47.2 5
	OSCC	10 0	0	52.6 8	11.1 0	24	75	47.7 5	54.0 0	60.0 0
	CONTR OL	10 0	0	32.3 0	9.48	19	62	24.0 0	32.0 0	37.0 0
serum CRP levels - mg/l	OSMF	10 0	0	14.3 7	7.82	4.30	45.23	7.46	11.4 5	20.6 0
	OSCC	10 0	0	49.3 3	24.8 1	13.46	114.22	36.6 4	46.3 2	63.6 1
	CONTR OL	10 0	0	3.32	1.33	1.22	6.24	2.34	3.24	4.32
Kruskal-Wallis										
	χ^2	df	p	ϵ^2						
age(yrs.)	109	2	<.001	0.36 5						
serum CRP levels -mg/l	242	2	<.001	0.80 9						

Tabel 4 shows Post hoc pairwise comparisons using the Dwass–Steel–Critchlow–Fligner method

Pairwise comparisons - age(yrs.)			
		W	p
OSMF	OSCC	9.84	<.001
OSMF	CONTROL	-5.71	<.001
OSCC	CONTROL	-14.08	<.001

Pairwise comparisons - serum CRP levels -mg/l			
		W	p
OSMF	OSCC	14.6	<.001
OSMF	CONTROL	-16.6	<.001
OSCC	CONTROL	-17.3	<.001

The descriptive analysis showed that the mean age was 39.26 ± 12.51 years in OSMF, 52.68 ± 11.10 years in OSCC, and 32.30 ± 9.48 years in controls. The median (50th percentile) values were 37.0 years for OSMF, 54.0 years for OSCC, and 32.0 years for controls, suggesting that participants with OSCC were relatively older.

For serum CRP levels, the mean values were 14.37 ± 7.82 mg/L in OSMF, 49.33 ± 24.81 mg/L in OSCC, and 3.32 ± 1.33 mg/L in controls, with median values of 11.45 mg/L, 46.32 mg/L, and 3.24 mg/L, respectively. The markedly higher CRP levels in OSCC patients indicate a strong inflammatory response in this group.

The Kruskal–Wallis test showed a statistically significant difference in age ($\chi^2 = 109$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.001$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.365$) and serum CRP levels ($\chi^2 = 242$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.001$, $\epsilon^2 = 0.809$) among the three groups, indicating that both variables varied significantly across OSMF, OSCC, and control participants.

Post hoc pairwise comparisons using the Dwass–Steel–Critchlow–Fligner method revealed that all intergroup differences were statistically significant. For age, the differences were significant between OSMF and OSCC ($W = 9.84$, $p < 0.001$), OSMF and controls ($W = -5.71$, $p < 0.001$), and OSCC and controls ($W = -14.08$, $p < 0.001$). Similarly, for serum CRP levels, significant differences were found between OSMF and OSCC ($W = 14.6$, $p < 0.001$), OSMF and controls ($W = -16.6$, $p < 0.001$), and OSCC and controls ($W = -17.3$, $p < 0.001$).

In summary, both age and serum CRP levels differed significantly among the three groups, with OSCC participants being older and exhibiting the highest mean CRP levels,

followed by OSMF, while controls showed the lowest values. This indicates a progressive elevation of systemic inflammation markers corresponding to disease severity.

Violin Plot

Violin Plot

Discussion

Inflammation is a protective biological response that serves to defend the body against invading pathogens. It is a complex, sequential process that functions to neutralize the initial cause of cellular injury, eliminate necrotic tissue, and initiate tissue repair and healing.^{19,20} Inflammation is broadly classified into two types: acute and chronic. In biological systems, acute inflammation generally plays a protective role, whereas chronic inflammation is strongly associated with carcinogenesis.²¹ In fact, inflammation is recognized as a precursor in the development of many tumors. Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) and oral submucous fibrosis (OSMF) are characterized by a complex inflammatory response. Inflammatory mediators and transcription factors serve as molecular links between inflammation and cancer. One such mediator is C-reactive protein (CRP), which bridges these two processes.¹⁹⁻²¹

Several studies have demonstrated a strong correlation between elevated CRP levels and adverse clinicopathological features such as bony erosion, extracapsular spread, nodal positivity, and advanced tumor stage. These findings suggest that increased CRP reflects chronic inflammation within the tumor microenvironment, which promotes angiogenesis and cellular proliferation while inhibiting apoptosis. Due to its short plasma half-life and consistent response to inflammatory stimuli, CRP is considered a reliable biomarker of inflammation. Given the close association between inflammation and carcinogenesis, CRP may also serve as a useful prognostic marker in malignancies.

In OSMF, initial mucosal irritation and discomfort progress to mucosal deterioration and ulceration. The initiation of oral mucosal inflammation by components of betel quid plays a critical role in the pathogenesis of OSMF. Pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin (IL)-6, tumor necrosis factor (TNF), and interferon- γ , along with growth factors including transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β), are produced at sites of inflammation.^{21,22} Within the tumor microenvironment, cytokines such as IL-6, IL-8, and TNF further contribute to the inflammatory milieu.

CRP, a member of the pentraxin family of proteins, is primarily synthesized by the liver in response to pro-inflammatory cytokines, particularly IL-6 and TNF- α . It serves as a dependable marker of disease activity and, to some extent, disease severity. Following tissue injury, CRP is produced as an acute-phase protein and is released into the bloodstream within a few hours, reflecting the presence of infection or inflammation.

In patients with OSCC, elevated preoperative CRP levels have been associated with larger tumor size, advanced disease stage, and reduced overall survival. Increased CRP levels may also indicate tumor invasiveness, including bone involvement, lymph node metastasis, and overall tumor burden. Furthermore, CRP has potential utility in the early detection and monitoring of precancerous lesions, thereby improving prognosis in individuals at risk of developing oral cancer.^{23,24}

Consequently, CRP not only reflects the inflammatory response within the tumor microenvironment but also indicates tumor-associated tissue destruction and localized cellular damage. This explains the elevated serum CRP levels observed in patients with OSCC and OSMF.²⁵

Previous studies have demonstrated the prognostic significance of C-reactive protein (CRP) in various systemic malignancies as well as in head and neck cancers.^{9,11–13} Elevated CRP levels have also been reported in oral potentially malignant disorders.^{1,3,15} In light of these findings, the present study was designed to evaluate serum CRP levels in patients with oral submucous fibrosis (OSMF) and oral cancer (OC), and to compare these values with those of healthy controls.

In the present study, the mean age of participants was highest in the oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) group (52.68 ± 11.10 years), followed by the OSMF group (39.26 ± 12.51 years) and the control group (32.30 ± 9.48 years). Overall, 75.3% of the participants were male and 24.7% were female. The healthy control group was age- and sex-matched with the study groups.

The findings of the present study are consistent with those reported by Shah et al.,²² Metgud et al.,¹¹ and More et al.²⁶ A clear male predominance was observed across all disease groups. This gender predilection may be attributed to the higher prevalence of tobacco and areca nut consumption among males compared to females in the Indian subcontinent.^{24,25}

In the present study, serum C-reactive protein (CRP) levels were measured and compared among all three study groups. The lowest serum CRP levels were observed in the healthy control (HC) group. A progressive increase in serum CRP levels was noted with increasing disease severity. Specifically, the mean serum CRP concentration increased from the HC group (3.32 ± 1.33 mg/L) to the oral submucous fibrosis (OSMF) group (14.37 ± 7.82 mg/L) and was highest in the oral cancer (OC) group (49.33 ± 24.81 mg/L).

These findings support the research hypothesis and suggest that serum CRP may serve as a potential biomarker for evaluating the role of inflammation in disease progression from normal oral mucosa to malignancy. Statistical analysis using the Kruskal–Wallis test revealed a statistically significant difference in serum CRP levels among the three groups.

Further intergroup comparisons of serum CRP concentrations between the healthy control group and the disease groups were performed using post hoc pairwise analysis with the Dwass–Steel–Critchlow–Fligner method. These comparisons demonstrated statistically significant differences between the HC group and both the OSMF and OC groups.

The results of the present study are in agreement with those reported by Vankadara et al.,¹ Gosavi et al.,¹⁹ Bhattacharjee et al.,²⁰ Uppal et al.,²⁷ Gupta et al.,²⁸ and Metgud et al.,¹¹, all of whom reported statistically significant differences in serum CRP levels among their respective study groups. However, the findings of the present study differ from those reported by Kaja et al.²⁹ and Kohli et al.³⁰, in which intergroup comparisons did not demonstrate statistically significant differences.

Limitations of the Study

The limitations of the present study include a non-uniform distribution of participants between genders. Additionally, the sample size could have been structured to include an equal distribution of participants across the different clinical stages of the disease groups. Such stratification would have enabled more robust intragroup comparisons of serum CRP levels and facilitated correlation of disease progression at both clinical and micro-molecular levels. Furthermore, oral potentially malignant disorders (OPMDs) other than oral submucous fibrosis (OSMF) were not included in the study. These limitations underscore the need for future studies with larger and more diverse populations, inclusion of other OPMDs, and evaluation of additional biomarkers to better elucidate the role of inflammation in oral carcinogenesis.

Conclusion

The findings of the present study demonstrate a progressive increase in serum C-reactive protein (CRP) levels with increasing disease severity. This suggests a strong association between elevated CRP levels and disease progression during oral carcinogenesis. The study establishes CRP as a reliable prognostic biomarker for oral potentially malignant disorders and oral cancer. Moreover, the present research provides baseline data for future investigations aimed at correlating serum CRP levels with various clinical stages of OPMDs as well as with histopathological grading of epithelial dysplasia. Further studies are warranted to evaluate the prognostic value of CRP in monitoring treatment response and predicting disease outcomes following therapeutic intervention.

References

1. Vankadara S, Padmaja K, Balmuri PK, Naresh G, Reddy VG. Evaluation of C-reactive protein levels in oral premalignancies and malignancies: A comparative study. *Journal of dentistry*. 2018; 15(6): 358-364.
2. Ray JG, Ganguly M, Rao BS, Mukherjee S, Mahato B, Chaudhuri K. Clinico-epidemiological profile of oral potentially malignant and malignant conditions among areca nut, tobacco and alcohol users in Eastern India: A hospital based study. *J Oral Maxillofac Pathol* 2013;17:45-50.
3. Warnakulasuriya S. Global epidemiology of oral and oropharyngeal cancer. *Oral Oncol* 2009;45:309-16.

4. Reddy v, Wanjari PV, Reddy N, Reddy P. Oral Submucous Fibrosis: Correlation of Clinical Grading to various habit factors. *Int J Of Dental Clinics* 2011;3(1):21-24.
5. Shetty SR, Babu SG, Kumari S, Rao V, Vijaya R, Karikal A. Malondialdehyde Levels in Oral Sub Mucous Fibrosis: A Clinicopathological and Biochemical Study. *N Am J Med Sci* 2012; 4(3): 125–128.
6. Chandrashekara S. C – Reactive protein: An inflammatory marker with specific role in physiology, pathology, and diagnosis. *IJRCI* 2014;2:1-23. [doi: 10.15305/ijrci/v2iS1/117].
7. Crosby D, Bhatia S, Brindle KM, Coussens LM, Dive C, Emberton M, et al. Early detection of cancer. *Science* 2022;375:eaay9040.
8. Welikala, R.A.; Remagnino, P.; Lim, J.H.; Chan, C.S.; Rajendran, S.; Kallarakkal, T.G.; Zain, R.B.; Jayasinghe, R.D.; Rimal, J.; Kerr, A.R.; et al. Automated Detection and Classification of Oral Lesions Using Deep Learning for Early Detection of Oral Cancer. *IEEE Access* 2020, 8, 132677–132693.
9. Warnakulasuriya, S.; Johnson, N.W.; Van DerWaal, I. Nomenclature and classification of potentially malignant disorders of the oral mucosa. *J. Oral Pathol. Med.* 2007, 36, 575–580.
10. Mahmood, H.; Shaban, M.; Indave, B.I.; Santos-Silva, A.R.; Rajpoot, N.; Khurram, S.A. Use of artificial intelligence in diagnosis of head and neck precancerous and cancerous lesions: A systematic review. *Oral Oncol.* 2020, 110, 104885.
11. Metgud, R.; Bajaj, S. Altered serum and salivary C-reactive protein levels in patients with oral premalignant lesions and oral squamous cell carcinoma. *Biotech. Histochem.* 2016, 91, 96–101.
12. Sudbo J. Novel management of oral cancer: A paradigm of predictive oncology. *Clin Med Res* 2004; 2(4): 233-242.
13. Anand Kumar C, Bhateja S. Altered C-reactive protein levels in serum of Oral precancer patients in comparison with healthy controls. *International journal of oral maxillofacial pathology.* 2011; 2(4): 16-19.
14. Mengji AK, Yaga US, Besta R, Soankamble S. C-reactive protein: An inflammatory biomarker in oral cancer. *J Indian Acad Oral Med Radiol* 2015;27:565-8.
15. Hart PC, Rajab IM, Alebraheem M, Potempa LA. C-reactive protein and cancer – Diagnostic and therapeutic insights. *Frontiers in immunology* 2020; 11.
16. Wang CS, Sun CF. C-reactive protein and malignancy: Clinico-pathological association and therapeutic implication. *Chang Gung Med J* 2009;32:471-82.
17. Chen Y, Cong R, Ji C, Ruan W. The prognostic role of C-reactive protein in patients with head and neck squamous cell carcinoma: A meta-analysis. *Cancer medicine* 2020; 9: 9541-53.
18. Tai SF, Chien HT, Young CK, Tsao CK, Palbo AD et al. Roles of preoperative C- reactive protein are more relevant in buccal cancer than other subsites. *World journal of surgical oncology.* 2017; 15:47
19. Gosavi SR, Torkadi AA. Serum C-reactive protein in oral submucous fibrosis and oral squamous cell carcinoma: A cross sectional study. *J Oral Maxillofac Pathol* 2020; 24: 46-51

20. Bhattacharjee K, Girish HC, Murgod S, Varsha VK, Nishanthi L, Sunder SV. Comparison of Serum C - Reactive protein level in Oral potentially Malignant disorders and in healthy individuals. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*. 2016; 7(2): 1285-90
21. Bala M, Braimah RO, Taiwo AO, Alyami B, Aliyu BM, Kanmodi KK, Abubakar SF, Kaura AM, Yekini LA, Yabo SU. Squamous cell carcinoma in the oral and maxillofacial region: A 12-year analysis at a tertiary healthcare facility from North-Western Nigeria. *J Cancer Tumor Int*. 2023 Dec;13(3):19–27.
22. Shah AP, Shah PH, Venkatesh R, Tinani K. Role of serum C-reactive protein levels in oral potentially malignant disorders and oral cancer: A cross-sectional study. *Oral Maxillofac Pathol J*. 2024 Jan;15(1).
23. Nozoe T, Saeki H, Sugimachi K: Significance of preoperative elevation of serum C-reactive protein as an indicator of prognosis in esophageal carcinoma. *Am J Surg*. 2001, 182:197-201.
24. Gockel I, Dirksen K, Messow CM, Junginger T: Significance of preoperative C-reactive protein as a parameter of the perioperative course and long-term prognosis in squamous cell carcinoma and adenocarcinoma of the oesophagus. *World J Gastroenterol*. 2006, 12:3746-50.
25. Rani K, Deb N, Sinha NK, Kumar U. CRP and lipid profile in oral cancer, leukoplakia and oral submucous fibrosis. *Int J Acad Med Pharm*. 2024;6(1):1802–5.
26. More CB, Rao NR, More S, Johnson NW. (2020) Reasons for Initiation of Areca Nut and Related Products in Patients with Oral Submucous Fibrosis within an Endemic Area in Gujarat, India. *Substance Use & Misuse*. 2020; 55(9): 1413-1421
27. Uppal MK, Iyengar AR, Subash BV, Patil S, Sharma ML, Thakar S. Estimation and correlation of serum and salivary C-reactive protein in oral potentially malignant disorders. *J Indian Acad Oral Med Radiol* 2021; 33:47-52
28. Gupta S, Tyagi N, Nadaf A. Serum and salivary C-reactive protein in patients with oral leukoplakia and squamous cell carcinoma. *International Journal of Research and Review*. 2019; 6(7):40-44
29. Kaja S, Naga SS, Kumar KK, Dasari N, Kantheti LC, Reddy BR. Quantitative analysis of C-reactive protein in potentially malignant disorders: A pilot study. *J Orofac Sci* 2015;7:3-6.
30. Kohli S, Gharote H, Shinde CV. Estimation of serum C-reactive protein in Oral Submucous Fibrosis. *Journal of dental and orofacial research* 2021; 17(1): 6-11.